

THE USE OF BILINGUAL METHODS IN IMPROVING THE COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE OF STUDENTS

Nurullayeva Nigora Nazirovna

Lecturer at Urgench State University

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Abstract. *Concepts such as bilingualism, bilingualism, multilingualism, multilingualism, multilingualism and plurilingualism are conceptual-level terms that serve as the basis for the formation of appropriate linguodidactic terms. The concepts of bilingualism (bilingualism) and multilingualism (multilingualism) are noted by many researchers as similar, where bilingualism is considered as a special case of multilingualism. At the same time, earlier bilingualism was assumed to be fluency in two languages, but over time the importance of the level of proficiency was leveled. Thus, both a native speaker of two languages and a person who has mastered one foreign language (in addition to his native one) is bilingual.*

Keywords: *bilingual learning, multilingual learning, multilingual learning, multilingual learning, bilingualism, bilingualism, multilingualism, multilingualism, multilingualism, multilingualism and plurilingualism.*

The concepts of bilingualism (bilingualism) and multilingualism (multilingualism) are noted by many researchers as similar, where bilingualism is considered as a special case of multilingualism [1]. At the same time, bilingualism was previously assumed to be fluency in two languages [2], but over time, the importance of the level of proficiency was leveled [3]. Thus, both a native speaker of two languages and a person who has mastered one foreign language (in addition to his native language) is a bilingual [4].

There are several types of bilingualism - composite (two ways to implement the concept, for example, a child can communicate at home in two languages - in the mother's native language and in the father's native language), coordinate (each language is used for its own system of concepts, for example, a Russian-speaking person working in Spain at an enterprise will use Spanish to designate a system of terms in a working environment) and subordinative (characterizing the study of a foreign language at school, when the study of a second language is based on the first - native - language) [5].

The term "diglossia" is also used to denote natural bilingualism and is used in a situation where two languages coexist on the same territory (for example, Belgium), or when it comes to the coexistence of two forms of one language [6].

The concept of multilingualism is characterized by both greater prevalence and the greatest vagueness, which causes a lot of controversy and controversy about its application. Sometimes the term "multilingualism" is equated with the terms "multilingualism" and "multilingualism" and means "the use of several languages within a certain social community" [7]. This interpretation of the term is used to describe a situation when more than two languages are functioning simultaneously on the territory of one country or on the territory of the Commonwealth of several countries (as in the case of the European Union). At the same time, the phenomenon of multilingualism can be considered from two positions: in relation to society as a whole - national multilingualism, and in relation to an individual who speaks several languages - individual multilingualism.

The dictionary of methodological terms and concepts by E. G. Asimov and A. N. Shchukin reveals the meaning of the concept of "multilingualism" in the field of language teaching methods: "a common provision in the European education system, according to which a modern person should speak two foreign languages besides his native one" [8].

The term "multilingualism" appeared in the works researchers in the field of linguodidactics as a tracing paper from English "multilingualism" and began to be used as an equivalent of "multilingualism" or "polylinguism". The works of French-speaking, Spanish-speaking and English-speaking researchers on linguodidactics use the term "multilingualism" (English) and, accordingly, the term "multilingual education" derived from it (]. In fact, both Western and Russian scientists use the term "multilingual education" to describe and solve problems related to teaching and learning several languages [9].

The term "multilingualism" is presented as a synonym for the term "multilingualism" and is defined through the latter. Public polylingualism refers to the functioning of several languages in society. Under individual - the use of several languages by one person [5]. At the same time, the level of development of types of speech activity in different languages may be different: a person can read in one foreign language and speak in another. There is no need to know languages at the same level [6].

Consider the meaning of the term "plurilingualism". It should be noted that in the dictionary of methodological terms and concepts by E. G. Asimov and A. N. Shchukin [3], in principle, there is no term from the formants "plurilingual" (plurilingual). His search in the Russian-language scientific literature was also difficult. A.V. Hackett-Jones [1] and V. M. Smokotin [6] refer us to foreign sources for clarification of "plurilingual" terms.

Let us turn to the materials posted on the website of The European Observatory for Plurilinguism (The European Observatory for Plurilinguism), namely to the document entitled "European Charter of Plurilinguism" [7]. On the first pages of the charter, a distinction is made between terms, where plurilingualism means the possession of several languages by one individual, and multilingualism (or "multilingualism" - a term appearing in the official translation of the charter - the presence of several languages on the same territory.

Thus, a plurilingual society consists of individuals who speak several languages at different levels, whereas a multilingual society may include a significant number of monolingual individuals, that is, people who speak only one language. In other words, the term "plurilingualism" corresponds to the term of Russian sociolinguistics "individual multilingualism". However, with the apparent sociolinguistic correspondence, we cannot conclude about the complete identity of their derivatives in the plane of linguodidactics.

The term "plurilingualism" (English plurilingualism) is widely used in the works of foreign researchers and is practically absent in the works of domestic methodologists. This is justified by the similar semantics of the concepts of "multilingualism", "plurilingualism" and "multilingualism", which casts doubt on the need to introduce a new term into the everyday use of linguodidactics. Moreover, the term "multilingual and multicultural competence" appearing in the document "Pan-European competences of foreign language proficiency: study, teaching, assessment" [5] corresponds in the English version of this document to the term "plurilingual and pluricultural competence". Thus, in the Russian methodology, the term "multilingualism" is officially fixed in the document as an analogue of the term "plurilingual".

However, at the conceptual level, the term "plurilingual" has its own interpretation [2]. The fact is that the European Union has based its language policy on a new concept - the concept of plurilinguism, documented in the "European Charter of Plurilinguism" and disclosed in the article by K. Tremblay. The Observatory's website has both the original article in French and the translation into Russian in open access [4].

K. Tremblay [1] distinguishes the terms "multilingualism" and "plurilingualism", arguing that each of them is characterized by its own concept. The differentiation, or even opposition, of these terms becomes obvious at the conceptual level.

Multilingual education in the modern interpretation, although it largely intersects with the mentioned directions in terms of content, still has its own distinctive characteristics. Taking into account the conditions of a multidisciplinary university and summarizing the comparative analysis carried out, we propose to define multilingual education as an organized process of teaching several foreign languages in an artificial environment with each language assigned its own functionality that determines the content of training and the level of training, as well as with the construction of the educational process not "from the content", but "from educational actions" a student.

With the development of science, both the terms "multilingual training / education" and "multilingual training / education" reveal similarities with the term "plurilingual training / education" accepted in foreign linguodidactics. In a broad context, both directions can be combined within the framework of multilingual education.

The goal of multilingual learning is to form multilingual communicative competence, which at the documentary level is synonymous with the foreign term "plurilingual competence". The task of the teacher, in accordance with the goal, is to show the student how to use his language repertoire to solve communication problems and how to work on its expansion.

With an increase in the number of languages taught, the emphasis is on coordinating the methodological content, rather than combining several foreign languages in one lesson. The use of two foreign languages in one lesson is allowed (as well as the study of a second foreign language through the first), but is not a mandatory characteristic of modern multilingual learning.

On the basis of a comparative analysis of approaches to the definition of multilingual competence, the definition of multilingual competence is formulated, applicable for the organization of multilingual education in the environment of a multidisciplinary university. Multilingual competence is the ability and willingness to carry out communicative activities with the help of a language repertoire, where the degree of proficiency in each language is determined by the scope of its application, the set of competencies and the level.

The component composition of multilingual competence is presented, which includes three components: integrative competence, general speech competence and professionally-oriented speech competence.

The content and implementation of the principles of organizing multilingual education in a multidisciplinary university are listed and described in detail, namely the principle of integrativity, the principle of basic educational strategies, the principle of organizing educational and cognitive activity from flexible skills, the principle of situational afferentation, the principle of reverse afferentation, the principle of minimizing intra-linguistic interference, the principle of iterative-level organization.

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